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Pantayong Pananaw sa Kasaysayan ng Pilipinas: The Perspective of a Filipino Gen Z's

Antonio G. Rivera Jr., LPT. ^[1]
Leah C. Jimeno, MA CDDS-SS ^[2]
National University – MOA, Pasay

The Filipino spirit has a multi-layered woven with threads of resilience, hope, and love for family and society. It is truly that the Philippines is the only country who were colonized by the powerhouse countries such as United States of America and Japan to name a few. This article intends to provide an inclusive and holistic understanding to the historical events of the Philippines from the point of view of a Filipino Generation Z. Philippine History is a people's history. It is a recorded struggle of people for ever increasing freedom and for newer and realization of the human person (Constantino & Ikehata, 1975)

The "Pantayong Pananaw sa Kasaysayan ng Pilipinas" has been circulating the internet but what is noteworthy are of Zeus Salazar, a Filipino historian proponent of *Pantayong Pananaw*, is "*Ang Pantayong Pananaw ay isang diskursong pangkabihasnan na naglalaman ng pag-uugnay ng halaga, kaalaman, at karanasan ng isang kultura sa pamamagitan ng iisang wika, naglalayong magkaroon ng kolektibong pag-unawa*" (Salazar, 1991) and Reynaldo Ileto, a Filipino historian best known for his landmark work *Pasyon and Revolution*, pointed out in his article that not all history is preserved and as it is important since it shapes nationalism and drives the revolution in the Philippines.

According to Ileto (1979), in the chapter entitled 'History from Below', the heroes' perspectives are not solely about selling our own country for the Philippines to gain independence but have something to do with the drive of faith. Majority of the written history is about the revolution against colonizers that will lead our country free from them. One would wonder how ironic certain circumstances are. We all know that most of the *Katipuneros* are composed of *Indios* and uneducated farmers. How these people perceive the movement. How uneducated farmers understand the things that they fight for and how come they actually believe in the beliefs of Andres Bonifacio and Jose Rizal. Simply because these personalities are elites. They have the means to understand at least the philosophy of enlightenment; they were able to study, and from there, these farmers and *Indios* were able to get the connection that they needed to fight for their freedom and for the *Inang Bayan*. In reviewing Philippine history, conventional historical accounts center on the governance of elites and the Spanish reign over the Philippines. Such narratives sideline the contributions and struggles of indigenous communities and the working classes.

"*Ang Kasaysayan ay Salaysay hinggil sa nakaraan o nakalipas na may Saysay*" (Salazar, 1999). One of the most famous lines that we can derive from Zeus Salazar's "*Pantayong Pananaw*" is when he discussed the word "*Kasaysayan*" as having two important ideas: "*Salaysay*," which means story, and "*Saysay*," which means relevance. Salazar clearly states that all history has a meaning and is not just simply laying out the stories of events. Each event has to be stressed to know why it is important to study history. Why is it that history taught to the youth is always about the suffering of the Filipinos during imperialism? Salazar's article focuses on first, the influence of Filipino elites on culture and identity under colonialists. Second, evolution of Filipino identity through language, standard of education and experiences of the

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people. Finally, the role of *ilustrados* in shaping intellectual discourse and societal dynamics. A younger generation might ask what the life of Jose Rizal have to do with them, it's funny to think but that's a valid question. These are the ones explained by Salazar that the learning of history does not end with the memorization of dates, people and events but it must be given meaning in the present so that it is given importance.

From the articles of the two Filipino historians, a big question arose in the world of academia - Can the studies and perspectives that have been exposed be considered timely and relevant, especially in our status quo? To strengthen the ideas, the authors conducted an oral interview with a millennial and a Generation Z. This was done to solicit the perspective of academic experts and draw attention to the lack of Filipino perspective on Philippine History. Based on the gathered statements, it is clear that there is a significant gap in Filipino Generation Z's understanding of Philippine history. Both generations emphasized the importance of understanding history from multiple perspectives and being aware of biases in historical records. Aside from this concern, there is a lack of deep appreciation for the country's cultural evolution, indigenous Filipino identity, and society. However, this gap is not limited to the younger generation's understanding of history, but also to the way these people in academia taught history; it should focus on cultivating critical thinking and questioning learners' opinions in order to make history more engaging and relevant to the current age. Understanding different historical perspectives is very important these days because it gives us an idea about how cultural changes have taken place and what were the norms of the societies which in turn helps us to deal with complex issues having a wider understanding of where we have come from. Telling new stories about old events — inclusive historical narratives that challenge traditional viewpoints we have been taught — may come closer to mending social problems by encouraging critical thinking and empathy while also understanding that these problems have deep roots in history.

Being a Filipino Generation Z, we can attest that the statements of historians such as Zeus Salazar and Reynaldo Ileto and other academician's perspective is timely due to the fact that they all emphasized the significance not only those common written history but also those unique stories and experiences of different sectors of society that helped to shaped our history. They all highlighted the events that may have been buried deep perhaps due to the mountainous information scattered and published on the internet, especially on social media. Indeed, our generation is blessed to be given the opportunity to hear perspectives from legit historians and academicians that allow us to value and embrace our beautiful history. This opened our eyes to rely solely no longer on the accounts of traditional historians; we must also consider the voices and experiences of ordinary Filipinos from different walks of life to gain a holistic understanding of our colorful past stories. Just like the work of Salazar and Ileto, it is fitting to have an inclusive and diverse history that does not only focus on the contributions of famous people, but also from the collective true experiences and struggles of all Filipinos.

By embracing "Pantayong Pananaw", we can gain broader and deeper knowledge and understanding of our fascinating history. In addition, these perspectives are of great help in shaping the knowledge and thinking ability of a Filipino Generation Z. Thorough questioning and genuine curiosity about our origins and the search for alternative perspectives that may pave the way to understanding our true history led us to a more just and equal society shaped by equality, unity, and social justice.

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